

**Studies on the Extractive Behaviour of 12-Heteropoly Acids:
Part III. Extraction of 12-Tungstophosphoric, 12-Molybdophosphoric,
12-Tungstosilicic and 12-Molybdosilicic Acids by
TBP in Organic Diluents**

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The extractions of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$, $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$, $H_4SiW_{12}O_{40}$ and $H_4SiMo_{12}O_{40}$ by TBP in benzene and nitrobenzene have been investigated. Evidence is provided to support the view that three molecules of TBP are associated with each molecule of the 12-heteropoly-acid extracted into the organic phase. The extraction equilibrium constant for each system has been determined.

Extraction studies^{1,2} have shown that 12-heteropoly acids are extracted into oxygenated organic solvents in the form of solvated ion pairs and their extractions are profoundly influenced by the basicity and dielectric constant of organic solvents. The number of solvent molecules participating in the extraction process are not known because of the use of pure solvents as extractants. The present work describes the extractions of 12-tungstophosphoric ($H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$), 12-molybdophosphoric ($H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$), 12-tungstosilicic ($H_4SiW_{12}O_{40}$) and 12-molybdosilicic ($H_4SiMo_{12}O_{40}$) acids by TBP in organic diluents such as benzene and nitrobenzene which are known to be poor extractants for these acids. The solvation number and the extraction equilibrium constant for each system have been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus and Reagents: Apparatus and the procedures for the preparations of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$, $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$, $H_4SiW_{12}O_{40}$ and $H_4SiMo_{12}O_{40}$ are reported elsewhere^{1,2}. Radioisotopes were obtained from Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay.

Reagents and solvents, except TBP, were of A.R. grade. Solvents were distilled in an all glass apparatus and the fractions distilling at their boiling points were collected and used for extraction studies. C.P. Grade TBP was purified by following the procedure described by Whitney and Diamond³.

A mixture of 100 ml. of TBP and 500 ml. of 0.1N NaOH was distilled at atmospheric pressure to remove volatile impurities. After collecting 200 ml. of distillate, TBP remaining in the distilling flask was made free from soluble impurities by washing with water until a pH of 6.5 was reached. It was then warmed under vacuum to remove water.

1. V. I. Lakshmanan and B. C. Haldar, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 512
2. V. I. Lakshmanan and B. C. Haldar, under publication.
3. D. C. Whitney and K. M. Diamond, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, 67, 2963.

Extraction Procedure : An aliquot (25 ml) of aqueous solution containing labelled $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$, $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$, $H_3SiW_{12}O_{40}$ or $H_4SiMo_{12}O_{40}$ was taken in a 100-ml separatory funnel and equilibrated for two minutes with an equal volume of solution of TBP in organic diluent. The two layers were allowed to separate and the top layer was first pipetted out. The bottom layer was then removed by opening the stop cock. Each solution was centrifuged. 5 ml of each phase were evaporated to dryness and activity was measured on a G.M. counter or on a Gamma-ray spectrometer provided with a single channel pulse-height analyzer. It was tested separately that extraction equilibrium was reached within two minutes of equilibration time. Each extraction was repeated at least thrice to check the reproducibility of the results.

DISCUSSION

The extractions of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ (Table I) and $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$ (Table II) by a 10% solution of TBP in benzene are found to be at least hundred times greater than their extractions into pure benzene. With TBP concentration in the range 4–10%, the slope of the straight line

Fig. 1 : Extraction of 12-tungsto- and 12-molybdo-phosphoric acids with TBP in benzene. Slope = 3.
 O — $4.07 \times 10^{-3} M H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$.
 Δ — $8.14 \times 10^{-3} M H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$.
 □ — $2.00 \times 10^{-3} M H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$.
 × — $1.00 \times 10^{-3} M H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$.

graph (Fig. 1) is found to be three. This may be interpreted to suggest that three molecules of TBP are associated with each molecule of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ and $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$ extracted into

benzene. The formation and extraction of 1 : 3 species are in agreement with the reported extractive behaviour of other strong acids and complex metal acids with TBP in non-polar organic solvents³.

TABLE I

Extraction of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid with TBP in Organic Diluents

Temperature : $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$

Conc. of TBP (in molarity)	Conc. of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ (in molarity)	Extraction Coefficient			
		4.07×10^{-3}		2.03×10^{-3}	
		<i>E</i> Benzene	<i>E</i> Nitrobenzene	<i>E</i> Benzene	<i>E</i> Nitrobenzene
0.119			2.206	3.13	
0.1492		3.8×10^{-4}	4.544	6.42	4.6×10^{-4}
0.1865		4.3×10^{-4}	6.01	7.92	5.6×10^{-4}
0.2238		6.3×10^{-3}	8.72	9.62	1.15×10^{-3}
0.2611		8.13×10^{-4}	—	12.3	—
0.2984		2.47×10^{-4}	10.5	10.4	2.81×10^{-4}
0.3730		2.90×10^{-3}	15.3		4.20×10^{-3}
0.4476		0.1047			
0.5222		0.331			
0.5968		0.739			
0.7460		1.92			

TABLE II

Extraction of 12-Molybdophosphoric Acid with TBP in Organic Diluents

Temperature : $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$

Conc. of TBP (in molarity)	Conc. of $H_3PMO_{12}O_{40}$ (in molarity)	Extraction Coefficient			
		1.0×10^{-3}		8.9×10^{-2}	
		<i>E</i> -Benzene	<i>E</i> -Nitrobenzene	<i>E</i> -Benzene	<i>E</i> -Nitrobenzene
0.119			3.67	0.86	
0.1492		1.02×10^{-4}	—	1.69	1.6×10^{-4}
0.1865		—	6.08	3.28	3.9×10^{-4}
0.2238		2.28×10^{-4}	8.59	5.90	5.9×10^{-4}
0.2611		3.88×10^{-4}	—	—	—
0.2984		7.26×10^{-4}	12.94	16.8	3.0×10^{-3}
0.3367		1.177×10^{-3}	—	—	—
0.3730		1.32×10^{-3}	—	—	5.7×10^{-3}

Earlier studies^{1,2} have shown that the extraction equilibrium between an aqueous solution of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ or $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$ and an immiscible or slightly miscible organic solvent is described by

where $M = W$ or Mo ,

provided the dielectric constant of the solvent is not too high to cause dissociation of the extracted species in the organic phase. The extractions of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ and $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$ by TBP in benzene may, therefore, be represented as,

and
$$K_1 = \frac{(H^+ \cdot 3TBP \cdot H_2PM_{12}O_{40}^-)_o}{(H^+)^2 (HPM_{12}O_{40}^{2-}) (TBP)_o^3} = \frac{E}{(H^+)^2 (TBP)_o^3} \quad (1)$$

where subscripts 'o' denotes organic phase and other terms have usual significance. At constant hydrogen ion concentration of equilibrated aqueous phase, expression (1) predicts that E should be proportional to $(TBP)_o^3$, as observed experimentally. Since the extraction coefficients of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ and $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$ have low values under the experimental conditions employed, the hydrogen ion concentration of the equilibrated aqueous phase remains essentially constant when TBP concentration in benzene phase is varied from 4% to 10%. With variation in initial concentrations of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ and $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$, the hydrogen ion concentration of the equilibrated aqueous phase is different for each set of measurements and so straight line graphs paralld to each other are obtained. However, as expected, the values (Table III) of K_1 at two different concentrations agree within experimental error. The values of K_1 for $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ and $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$ are comparable.

TABLE III

Determination of Extraction Constant for 12-Heteropoly Acids (TBP in Benzene)

Temperature : $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$

Heteropoly acid	Conc. of 12-heteropoly acid (in molarity)	$\log K_1 = \log E + 2pH$ $- 3 \log (TBP)$
$H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$	8.1×10^{-3}	2.5 ± 0.20
	4.07×10^{-3}	2.4 ± 0.20
$H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$	2.0×10^{-3}	2.2 ± 0.20
	1.0×10^{-3}	2.6 ± 0.30

With TBP concentration in the range 10–20%, the plot of $\log E$ versus $\log (TBP)_o$ gives a straight line with slope nearly equal to 10. It is difficult to interpret experimental data obtained with such concentrated solutions (10–20%) of TBP, because the organic phase cannot be assumed to show ideal behaviour and may not have the properties of the inert diluent (benzene) employed. Attempts to determine the number of water molecules extracted

into benzene solution (4–10%) of TBP were not successful due to the reaction of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ and $\text{H}_3\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ with Karl-Fischer reagent. Extraction studies of $\text{H}_4\text{SiW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ and $\text{H}_4\text{SiMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ with TBP in benzene revealed that the extraction coefficient values are too low to provide extraction data of sufficient accuracy.

In the extraction of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ (Table I) and $\text{H}_3\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ (Table II) by TBP in nitrobenzene, the extracted species is expected to undergo ionization in the organic phase. The extraction equilibrium can be written as

and the extraction equilibrium constant, K_2 , is given by

$$K_2 = \frac{[\text{H}(\text{x TBP})]_0^+ [\text{H}_2\text{PM}_{12}\text{O}_{40}(\text{n-x})\text{TBP}]_0^-}{(\text{H}^+)^2 (\text{HPM}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{2-}) (\text{TBP})_0^n} \quad (2)$$

since $(\text{H}^+) = 2(\text{HPM}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{2-})$

and

$$\text{H}^+(\text{x TBP})_0^+ = (\text{H}_2\text{PM}_{12}\text{O}_{40}(\text{n-x})\text{TBP})_0^-$$

equation (2) can be changed into

$$K_3 = \frac{E^2}{(\text{H}^+)(\text{TBP})_0^n} \quad (3a)$$

or

$$2 \log E + pH = n \log (\text{TBP})_0 + \log K_2 \quad (3b)$$

where $K_3 = 2K_2$. It follows from expression (3b) that a straight line graph should result from the plot of $(2 \log E + pH)$ against $\log(\text{TBP})_0$ and its slope would give the number of TBP

Fig. 2 : Extraction of 12-tungsto- and 12-molybdo-phosphoric acids with TBP in nitrobenzene.

O — $2.04 \times 10^{-3} M \text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$.

Δ — $6.46 \times 10^{-3} M \text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$.

X — $6.7 \times 10^{-3} M \text{H}_3\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$.

molecules associated with the extracted species. Figure 2 shows that the slope of the straight line obtained by plotting experimental data as $(2 \log E + pH)$ versus $\log (TBP)_0$ approximates to 3, which means that the extracted species contain three molecules of TBP per acid molecule. The values of K_3 remain fairly constant with variation in the initial concentrations of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ and $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$.

Fig. 3 : Extraction of 12-tungsto- and 12-molybdo-silicic acids with TBP in nitrobenzene.

□ — $3.1 \times 10^{-3} M H_4SiW_{12}O_{40}$.

▲ — $10.3 \times 10^{-3} M H_4SiW_{12}O_{40}$.

⊙ — $2.8 \times 10^{-3} M H_4SiMo_{12}O_{40}$.

$H_4SiW_{12}O_{40}$ and $H_4SiMo_{12}O_{40}$ are extracted into nitrobenzene with first-power (Figure 3) TBP dependency. Considering that each of $H_4SiW_{12}O_{40}$ and $H_4Mo_{12}O_{40}$ dissociates in nitrobenzene to produce three ions, the extraction equilibrium may be expressed as

and the equilibrium constant

$$K_4 = \frac{(H^+ \cdot xTBP)_0^2 (H_2SiM_{12}O_{40}^{2-} \cdot (n-x)TBP)_0}{(H^+)^2 (H_2SiM_{12}O_{40}^{2-}) (TBP)_0^n} \quad (4a)$$

Since $[H^+ \cdot xTBP]^+ = 2(H_2SiM_{12}O_{40}^{2-})(n-x)TBP)_0$ and $(H^+) = 2(H_2SiM_{12}O_{40}^{2-})$, equation (4a) can be written

$$K_4 = \frac{E^3}{(TBP)_0^n} \quad (4b)$$

or

$$\log E = \frac{n}{3} \log (TBP)_0 + \frac{1}{3} \log K_4 \quad (4c)$$

It may be inferred from equation (4c) that the first-power TBP dependency as observed experimentally corresponds to n equal to 3 or in other words, three molecules of TBP are associated with one molecule of the extracted species in nitrobenzene. For $n = 3$, the values of $\log K_4$ calculated with the help of equation (4c) are given in Table V.

TABLE IV

*Determination of Extraction Constant for 12-Heteropoly Acids (TBP in Nitrobenzene)*Temperature : $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$

Heteropoly-acid	Conc. of 12-heteropoly acid (in molarity)	$\log K_3 = 2 \log E + pH$ $- 3 \log (TBP)_o$
$H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$	2.035×10^{-3}	7.50 ± 0.20
	6.46×10^{-3}	7.30 ± 0.20
$H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$	6.7×10^{-3}	6.9 ± 0.30
	1.89×10^{-2}	6.7 ± 0.30

TABLE V

*Determination of Extraction Constant for 12-tungsto- and 12-molybdo- silicic acids with TBP in Nitrobenzene*Temperature : $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$

12-Heteropoly acid	Conc. of 12-heteropoly acid (in molarity)	$\log K_4 = 3(\log E - \log TBP)$
$H_4SiW_{12}O_{40}$	3.10×10^{-3}	-2.7 ± 0.3
	10.3×10^{-3}	-2.4 ± 0.2
$H_4SiMo_{12}O_{40}$	2.8×10^{-3}	-1.50 ± 0.15

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